

PEDAGOGICAL SKILLS OF A PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHER

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Abstract. *The relevance of the research at the scientific and methodological level is determined by the contradiction between the actual practice of improving the pedagogical skills of a physical education teacher and the degree of its scientific and theoretical justification, which does not allow it to be brought to the technological level. The author describes ways to improve the pedagogical skills of a teacher in the discipline of physical culture.*

Keywords: *skill, profession, pedagogical technology, emotion, artistry, educational process, pedagogical technique.*

The improvement of pedagogical skills is carried out as an accompanying, secondary component of professional activity; its structural components have not been determined, technologies have not been created and conditions of formation have not been identified, which negatively affects not only the level of professional competence, but also reduces the level of personal satisfaction in the profession.

Pedagogical technology is a complex of knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for a teacher to solve strategic, tactical, as well as procedural tasks during the educational process. Pedagogical technology is a description of the system of actions of a teacher with students that should be performed for the optimal implementation of the educational process.

The components of pedagogical technology are the mastery of the art of communication with students, the ability to direct their attention and the attention of students, the ability to find out their mental state by external signs of student behavior, the ability to establish optimal relationships with students.

The most important component of pedagogical skill is the culture of speech. The communicative qualities of a teacher usually include voice production, mimicry and pantomime, emotion management, mood, etc.

Desirable qualities include artistry, a sense of humor, sociability. This, of course, should also include goodwill towards students. It is well known that the final level of mastery of speech largely depends on the ability of the teacher to create an emotionally relaxed atmosphere of the lesson

Pedagogical mastery is also considered as a manifestation of one's own "I" in the profession, as the self-realization of the teacher's personality in pedagogical activity, therefore, it is defined as his highest, creative activity, which provides for the expedient use of methods and means of pedagogical interaction in every situation of study and upbringing.

Knowledge of the subject from the inside, based on a high sports title and personal experience, is the basis for the creativity of the teacher, both in the field of sports discipline and in the methodology of his teaching. Genuine creativity is based on the completeness of information, scientific forecast, the ability of the teacher to apply different combinations of means, forms and methods of pedagogical influence in the educational process in a new and effective way each time.

Pedagogical technique involves: the ability to rely on didactic principles; the ability to take into account the requirements of the principles of sports training, as well as a number of professional pedagogical skills [2]. With the development of pedagogy and psychology as a science and practical activity, next to the concept of "pedagogical technique", which reflects only the subjective features of the educational process, the term "pedagogical technology" (knowledge of mastery) began to be used, which concerns the problems of planning the organization of the educational process.

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The famous psychologist V.A.Kan-Kalik distinguished the following styles of pedagogical communication:

1. Communication based on high professional attitudes of the teacher, his attitude to pedagogical activity in general.
2. Communication based on a friendly disposition.
3. Communication-distance refers to the most common types of pedagogical communication.
4. Communication-intimidation is a negative form of communication, inhumane, revealing the pedagogical inconsistency of the teacher resorting to it.
5. Communication is flirting, typical for young teachers striving for popularity.

Pedagogical style is a set of peculiar thoughts and actions of teachers (of one school, epoch) that distinguishes them from other teachers (of another school, epoch). The style of educational work is uniquely individual. The teacher should always be friendly, cheerful; carefully think over the content of classes, conduct it only in a sports uniform that meets modern aesthetic requirements, observe work discipline and conscientiously perform their professional duties [3].

The optimal style is characterized by a conviction in a worldview position, the desire for constant self-improvement, a multidirectional positive attitude to business, to oneself, to the educated. The successful achievement of the set educational, training and educational goals testifies to the pedagogical skill of a specialist in physical culture. This is especially typical for those cases when a negative situation develops, there is a low motivation of trainees for physical improvement, organizational and material difficulties arise, but educational issues are still solved.

In addition, the presence of professional pedagogical skills is evidenced by the mandatory solution of the most important educational tasks, the formation of important personal qualities [2].

Conclusions. Pedagogical mastery is the highest level of pedagogical activity, the highest creative activity of a teacher. It is a synthesis of scientific knowledge, skills of methodical art and personal qualities of a teacher, a set of personality traits of a teacher, which provides a high level of self-organization of pedagogical activity. The teacher's skill represents a complex structure of terms containing at least four subsystems: pedagogical technology, pedagogical creativity, knowledge of the subject, pedagogical style.

One of the most important components of pedagogical skills is the culture of speech. In the field of the specifics of the educational subject, high demands are placed on the teacher of physical

education. Therefore, the successful achievement of the set educational, training and educational goals testifies to the pedagogical skill of a specialist in physical culture.

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